

THE OFFSHORE WIND POWER POTENTIAL OF THE BLACK AND AZOV SEAS

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Today, the renewable energy sector in Europe belongs to the established sectors of the economy and special attention is directed to the development of such areas of the Blue Economy as offshore wind energy. Currently, technologies for the use of offshore wind energy have become the main direction in the development of wind energy. Due to the lower water surface roughness compared to the earth's surface, the wind speed over the sea is usually 20 % higher than under the same conditions over the surrounding lands. This contributes to the production of much more energy from offshore wind farms than onshore.

The aim of this study is to determine the distribution of wind power density in the Black and Azov Seas, as well as to identify areas with the most favorable conditions for the placement of offshore wind turbines (OWT).

Potential wind energy resources are the total energy of the movement of air masses moving over a given territory during the year. The most accurate assessment of potential wind resources can be obtained using the wind power density, which is the energy characteristic of the wind, depending on the frequency of wind speeds and the nature of the underlying surface in a particular site. More precisely, its description can be obtained using the Weibull distribution for flat terrain conditions (Kobysheva, 2008):

$$f(u) = \frac{\gamma}{\beta} \left(\frac{u}{\beta} \right)^{\gamma-1} \exp \left[- \left(\frac{u}{\beta} \right)^{\gamma} \right]$$

where $f(u)$ is the frequency of occurrence of wind speed u , β – scaling factor (m/s), γ – the shape factor, which describes the shape of the distribution.

The wind power density can be estimated using the formula (Kobysheva, 2008):

$$N_e = \frac{1}{2} \rho \beta^3 \Gamma \left(\frac{3}{\gamma} + 1 \right)$$

where N_e – wind power density, ρ – air density (1.226 kg/m³), $\Gamma \left(\frac{3}{\gamma} + 1 \right)$ – gamma function.

According to the Global Wind Atlas, the value of N_e at 50 m height changes from 70-200 W/m² in the southeastern part of the Black Sea to 1048 W/m² in the Tsemesskaya Bay. In general, the spatial distribution N_e over the Black Sea shows an increase from the southeast, where the annual mean wind speed at 50 m height is about 5 m/s, to the northwest, where the wind speed is about 7 m/s. Based on the value N_e and the above requirements for location OWT, favorable conditions for the placement of large OWT have the following sites (Fig. 1, Table 1).

Table 1 Wind characteristics of sites with $N_e > 400$ W/m²

Plot number	$\bar{V}_{an}$, m/s	$N_{e100\%}$, W/m ²	$N_{e10\%}$, W/m ²	Wind power class	S, km ²	Depth H, m
1	7.0-7.2	422	445	4	45000	< 50
2	6.7-6.7	421	452	4	6600	< 1000
3	7.0-7.2	555	619	5 - 6	1340	< 1000
4	7.0-7.4	460	585	4 - 5	9000	< 1000
5	6.9-7.6	588	818	5 - 7	1650	< 1000
6	5.9-6.1	420	440	4	39	200-800
7	5.8-6.2	474	540	4 - 5	1080	< 1000
8	5.0-5.4	414	450	4	20	< 1000
9	6.4-6.8	460	520	4 - 5	715	< 1000
10	6.5-6.7	420	455	4	95	15-50
11	7.6-7.7	530	568	5	33000	< 14

Notes: $\bar{V}_{an}$ – annual mean wind speed at 50 m height;
 $N_{e100\%}$ – the mean annual wind power density over the territory at 50 m height for 100 % of the area of the selected site;
 $N_{e10\%}$ – the mean annual wind power density over the territory at 50 m height for 10 % of the area of the selected site with the highest wind rates

Based on the methodology described in the report «Going Global: Expanding Offshore Wind to Emerging Markets» (WBG, 2022), to accommodate OWT are suitable water areas that meet these conditions (WBG, 2019):

1. Annual mean wind speed greater than 7 m/s at 100 m height (6.3 m/s at 50 m height), for the current performance characteristics of OWT;
2. Water depth of less than 50 m – for fixed offshore wind farms;
3. Water depth between 50 to 1000 m – for floating wind farms;
4. Less than 200 km from shore;
5. Any isolated regions < 10 km² were excluded;
6. Constant turbine planting densities of 3 MW per km² for wind speeds between 7-8 m/s and 4 MW per km² for wind speeds greater than 8 m/s.

The assessment of the wind energy potential was made on the basis of wind data placed on the website of the Global Wind Atlas. This application (Global Wind Atlas) is specially designed to help identify areas with strong winds, suitable for wind turbines. As input data in the atlas were used ERA5 reanalysis data for 2008-2017 of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) with spatial resolution 30 km. As a result of the downscaling process, the user obtains the characteristics of the local wind climate with a grid spacing of 250 m at five heights: 10 m, 50 m, 100 m, 150 m and 200 m above the earth's surface (GWA, 2022).

Fig. 1 Annual mean N_e (W/m²) at 50 m height for 2008-2017 and schematic arrangement of sites with $N_e > 400$ W/m² and depths up to 1000 m

CONCLUSIONS. Thus, according to the Global Wind Atlas, most of the Black and Azov Seas are characterized by significant wind resources ($N_e > 400$ W/m²). The total area of sites with the fourth wind power class and above, as well as depths up to 1000 m, is about 98500 km².

On the north-western shelf of the Black Sea, as well as throughout the entire water area of the Azov Sea, there are significant areas with depths of less than 50 m and a distance from the coast of not more than 200 km, suitable for placing both floating and fixed OWT.

Significant water areas with high wind power classes in the northwestern and northeastern parts of the Black Sea, as well as the Azov Sea, allow the installation of offshore wind farms capable of generating energy on an industrial scale.

References
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